

RESULTS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF MSCT ANALYSIS IN STROKE DIAGNOSTICS

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Relevance: Blood veins clinical diagnosis good developed despite , it damage level and forecast to determine such as important problems solution does not That's it due to the diagnosis of stroke , first next , hemorrhagic and ischemic of a stroke differential diagnostics , as well as other diseases (first in line voluminous processes) with differential diagnosis to do necessary

Material and methods : to research Republic urgent medical help scientific center Surkhandarya branch urgent neurology 2024 in the department year January-July brain in months blood rotation sharp violation with of 60 sick patients disease history was studied . Patients from MSKT in diagnosis used and all to patients standard cure methods used .

Result : Analysis based on ischemic stroke 70 % (n=42) and hemorrhagic stroke was noted in 30% (n=18). done Left half in 25 patients in the ball , 28 of them right half in the ball and in 7 the brain column damaged .

In 31 patients (group I) MSKT method disease from the beginning in the first 1 hour used in 29 cases (group II) in the next 3-5 hours or from him later used . Differential cure measures are also relevant way later in group 2 started (from the conclusion of the MSKT after) .

First in the group of patients recovery earlier are complications less was

Conclusion : MSKT is not only of a stroke nature own in time diagnosis and ischemic the brain damage hemorrhagic transformation an exception do maybe the brain damage level assessment , infarction of the hearth localization identify , brain damage morphometry transfer enable gives Therapeutic of measures volume and tactics planning for his of the brain around to the parts effect level assessment , their efficiency observation and of the disease next development danger level in determining important importance occupation is enough